

6

Crafting “Whiteness” in Early America: A Critical Overview

Dr. Ayan Mondal,
Assistant Professor,
Department of English (UG & PG),
Bankura Christian College,
Bankura, West Bengal, India.

***Abstract:** “Whiteness” in America did not emerge from the blue. The category in fact “evolved” in early America validating the very claim that America “became” white more than manifesting the biological difference with the blacks. In fact the twentieth century saw the burgeoning of a distinctive discipline called “Whiteness Studies”. The present articles, however, focuses on what went into being in order to “craft” whiteness in early America covering the religious, cartographical and historical dimensions.*

Key Words: white, black, cartography, whiteness studies, craft

"One of the signs of the times is that we really don't know what 'white' is", asserts Kobena Mercer, and adds that "the real challenge in the new cultural politics of difference is to make 'whiteness' visible for the first time, as a culturally constructed ethnic identity historically contingent upon the disavowal and violent denial of difference" (Mercer 205-6). A pertinent concern that has preoccupied critical attention in the United States is the one that addresses the factors that have resulted in the nation's "becoming" white. The first thing that comes to mind is obviously the very "White" identity that was crystallized by way of the country being inhabited mostly by people from the British Isles as founders or early settlers. Such people already having a share of being colonial rulers, started treating the First Nations and blacks

in America as “Others” in terms of customs, habits, habitat, language and appearance and labelled them as cultureless brutes. Eventually, the task was to determine who was essentially “American” was and who was not. The American nation at one point of time started getting treated as an exclusively “white” nation, as the presence of the First Nations and the blacks gradually came to be obliterated at the cost of promoting the white settlers. Historians, ethnographers, legal documents and even some Constitutional precepts and amendments promoted this “self-inflated” amnesia of the American Nation. Pinder elaborates this “amnesia” in the following words:

This forgetfulness, this self-inflated amnesia is perfectly illustrated in the history told by David Ramsay who boasts that the Scots, Swiss, Irish, Germans, New Englanders, and Dutch “have been the sources from, which America derived her population”. Equally oblivious was the French political thinker Alex de Tocqueville who, when he visited the United States in 1830, described America and its citizens as “Anglo Americans”. All documents that defined America, including the Declaration of Independence, the Constitution and the Bill of Rights, contributed to promote a white America (40).

Dana Nelson, Cheryl I. Harris, Matthew Frye Jacobson likewise asserted how whiteness was gradually “crafted” and very tactfully manoeuvred in America through the unjust and discriminatory treatment of the non-whites, assigning them inferior subject-positions. Apart from social and political domination, “racial” domination was crucially essential to endorse their superiority. The Europeans, in the words of Oliver C. Cox, “have not been content merely to accept their present social and political dominance as an established fact. Almost from the first they have attempted to rationalize the situation and to prove to themselves that their subjugation of other racial groups was natural and inevitable” (qtd in Pinder 42). Though scholars like Gossett tried to ascribe the heathenism of the Native Americans and blacks as the basic cause

of their enslavement by their Puritan masters, it was evident that racism was already implanted in the minds of the European colonists from the older world.

Eric Williams argued in 1944 that “slavery was not born of racism: rather racism was the consequence of slavery”. Barbara Lewis Solow, Stanley L. Engerman, Oscar Handlin and Mary Handlin also held that slavery in America predated racism. The Handlins argued that initially the black indentured servants and their white counterparts were treated alike. However, “Bacon’s Rebellion of 1676” was the first significant historical phenomenon to create a gulf and a spirit of division between the white and the black servants. Both the racial groups responded to Nathaniel’s Bacon’s military call to raise arms against the Native Americans, although their individual aims were different. For the whites, the basic aim was to grab free lands for becoming prosperous farmers, whereas for the blacks it was the urge to put an end to their servitude through revolution. However, things turned out very different as the Rebellion resulted in a social hierarchy that was consciously created by the ruling class to make even the “poor” whites feel socially superior to blacks and non-whites. The white servants were entitled to new lands and their black counterparts remained the discriminated lot. Therefore, long before “slavery” was to officially get codified and initiated in America, the “colour prejudice” was paramount there. Whiteness and white-skin privilege, consequently got thoroughly established by the harmonious synchronization of the genesis of slavery and racial prejudices. In the *Harvard Law Review*, Cheryl I. Harris argued how by the 1660s the degraded status of Blacks as chattel slaves came to be strongly established by law. Harris argued:

Between 1680 and 1682, the first slave codes appeared, codifying the extreme deprivations of liberty already existing in social practice. Many laws parcelled out differential treatment based on racial categories: Blacks were not permitted to travel without permits, to own property, to assemble publicly, or to own weapons; nor

were they to be educated. Racial identity was further merged with stratified social and legal status: “Black” racial identity marked who was subject to enslavement; “white” racial identity marked who was “free” or, at minimum not a slave. The ideological and rhetorical move from “slave” and “free” to “Black” and “White” as polar constructs marked an important step in the social construction of race (Harris 1718).

This hierarchy got inscribed in the American psyche through laws, political pamphlets and other American institutions. A diachronic analysis of some of the laws and documents might validate this claim.

In Hector St John Crèvecoeur’s *Letters from an American Farmer* (1782), the much quoted passage reads:

What then is the American, this new man? He is either a European or the descendent of a European, hence that strange mixture of blood, which you will find in no other country. I could point out to you a family whose grandfather was an Englishman, whose wife was Dutch, whose son married a French woman, and whose present four sons have four wives of different nations. He is an American, who leaving behind him all his ancient prejudice and manners, receives new ones from the new mode of life he has embraced, the new government he obeys, and the new rank he holds. He becomes an American by being received into the broad lap of our great Alma mater. Here individuals are melted into a new race of men, whose labours and posterity will one day cause great changes in the world (43).

It is interesting to note that Crèvecoeur in his long list of ethnicities and nationalities did not include the Negroes, First Nations, the Chinese or other racialized ethnic groups. For Crèvecoeur, the American identity only signified the strange mixture of diverse European nationalities. It was already impregnated in the

American psyche that the normative identity in US was only the white American one. Pinder argued that even in contemporary times those Americans of European descent who thought of themselves in terms of their ethnicities (their Italianness, Greekness, or Jewishness) did not require to spare a separate thought on “whiteness” because whiteness for them functions as the unquestionable, singular norm. Pinder writes, “...whites as a race is never talked about because whites are the norm and discussions of race are traditionally applied only to demonstrate the perceived superiority of the “white race” over those who are looked on as non-white. Indeed when the question is asked, who is an American? Many researchers often find that whites view themselves as Americans and non-whites are viewed as hyphenated Americans...” (Pinder 73). Thus when Crèvecoeur was talking about the Americans being “melted” into the new race in the new land, he considered the blacks and the other racialized groups as the “unmeltable ethnics”.

Even Benjamin Franklin, one of the founding fathers of the nation argued in favour of a homogenous all-white America. In his essay “Observations Concerning the Increase of Mankind and the Peopling of Countries”, Franklin noted:

All Africa is black or tawny; Asia chiefly tawny; America (exclusive of the newcomers) wholly so. And in Europe, the Spaniards, Italians, French, Russians, Swedes are generally of what we call a swarthy complexion; as are the Germans also, the Saxons only excepted, who, with the English, make the principal body of white people on the face of earth. I could wish their numbers were increased. (Franklin 234)

Franklin’s wistfulness of a purely white America also propelled him to further ask “why should America in the sight of Superior beings, darken its people? Why increase the sons of Africa by planting them in America where we have so fair an opportunity by excluding of Blacks and Tawnies and increasing the lovely whites” (234). Therefore the imperative drive of placing the whites atop in

the racial ladder was deeply pervasive in Franklin's vision. The "Declaration of Independence" drafted by Thomas Jefferson, however, rung a politically correct affirmative note:

We hold these truths to be self-evident that all men are created equal, that they are endowed by their Creator with certain unalienable Rights that among these are Life, Liberty and the Pursuit of Happiness. That to secure these Rights, Governments are instituted among Men, deriving their just powers from the consent of the governed. (qtd in Sen and Sengupta 9)

Paradoxically enough, Jefferson's contention in "Declaration" was fraught with falsity and at best, was only a half-truth. When Jefferson was talking about equality of "all men" and the exercise of their "unalienable Rights" he thought only about men of his race, divided by ethnicities, united by their whiteness. Paul L. Ford argued in *The Works of Thomas Jefferson*, how Jefferson thought of the independent black nation, Santo Domingo to be an appropriate place for the blacks to reside. About Santo Domingo, Jefferson contended that it was "inhabited already by a people of their own [black] race and colour; climates congenial with their natural constitution; insulated from other descriptions of men" (Ford 317). Therefore, Jefferson strongly believed that it was impossible for blacks and whites to coexist in America, there being certain acrimonious racial differences between the two. Jefferson's idea of "equality" of all men underwent several critiques, some of which Pinder summed up very cogently:

The idea that "all men are equal" vexed some of the most important figures. In fact, for James Hamond, the former governor of South Carolina in the 1840s it was "ridiculously absurd". A decade later, "a self-evident lie" was the phrase used by the Senator John Pettit to Jefferson's notion of equality. As late as the 1980s, Pastor Richard G. Butler of the Aryan Nations noted, "When the *Declaration of Independence* talks about "one people", it's not talking about a nation made for Asia, Africa, [or] India.

Judging the rights of citizens based on the colour of their skin has certainly been an American pastime. (Pinder 55)

Several laws were promulgated and implemented in post-independence America to pioneer and champion “whiteness”. For instance the “Naturalization Act of 1790” read “all free white persons who have, or, shall migrate into the United States, and shall give satisfactory proof, before a magistrate by oath, that they intend to reside therein, and shall take an oath of allegiance, and shall have resided in the United States for one whole year, shall be entitled to the rights of citizenship” (“Annals of Congress” 184). The Act clearly had two-fold aims, as Pinder notes. First, to suppress slave rebellions and violent uprisings and second, to curtail the efforts of the First Nations to resist white infringements on their lands. Both the aims pointed at the fundamental premise of strengthening whiteness in the nation. Though this Act was slightly modified in 1802, by setting a five-year residence of new immigrants compulsory for new immigrants, the basic requirement of citizenship remained the same- celebration of “whiteness”. Cheryl I. Harris also added another dimension to this idea of “naturalization” of white citizens, where one’s “whiteness”, rather than owned “land” came to be counted as property. Harris argued-

Moreover the trajectory of expanding democratic rights for whites was accompanied by the contraction of the rights of Blacks in an ever deepening cycle of oppression. The franchise, for example, was broadened to extend voting rights to unpropertied white men at the same time that Black voters were specifically disenfranchised, arguably shifting the property required for voting from land to whiteness. (Harris 1744)

The “Bill of Rights” (the first ten amendments to the American Constitution between 1789 and 1791) was implemented to preserve and secure the basic rights, privileges and liberties of the white people in the newly constituted nation. Needless to mention that the First Nations and the blacks who were not naturalized as citizens of America were unprotected by these constitutional

amendments. In 1793, the “Fugitive Slave Act” was enacted by the American Congress to facilitate, within the frontiers of the United States, to facilitate capture and return of runaway slaves to their masters. The Act also imposed severe punishments on anyone assisting the flight of the runaways. This Act, therefore, attempted to commodify and objectify slaves as “properties”. In 1830, the power of “whiteness” became even more bolstered when President Andrew Jackson signed the “Indian Removal Act” that amounted to the forced removal of the First Nations from their homes. The Act enabled the President to grab lands possessed by the Indians within the US territory in exchange of unsettled lands towards the West of the Mississippi river. The Act therefore ensured almost a hegemonized monopoly of the whites in the US territory at the cost of exterminating the Native Americans. In 1850, another severe act ensuring the legal security of a white man was implemented- the “Act Concerning Civil Cases”. The Act stated- “No Black, or Mulatto person, or Indian shall be allowed to give evidence in favour of, or against a white man”. The Act was strongly taken recourse to by the California Supreme Court in 1854 when a white man was convicted. Pinder sums up the case as follows:

In *People v Hall*, in 1854, Hall, a white man charged with the murder of Ling Sing, a Chinese man, was convicted thanks to the testimony of three Chinese witnesses. But the California Supreme Court reversed the decision because, according to the Act Concerning Civil Cases, Chinese were also included in the law. The judge affirmed that the Chinese were” a race of people whom nature has marked as inferior, and who are incapable of progress or intellectual development beyond a certain point. (Pinder 58)

In 1875 the “Page Law” was introduced to put an end to cheap Chinese labour and “immoral”, “lascivious” Chinese women from entering the US. The law not merely barred such immigrants, but also imposed a ban against coolie labourers by announcing severe punishments if they attempted to bring persons from China, Japan or any of the East Asian countries to the US. Adverse attitudes

towards the Chinese-Americans aggravated in a series of acts and finally culminated in the “Chinese Exclusion Act” passed in 1882 that suspended immigration of Chinese men for the next ten years and denied dignity and citizenship to the Chinese who were already residing in America. Pinder has it right when he comments “The Chinese Exclusion Act was part of a tyrannical policy that was modified and extended in various ways to Japanese, Filipino, Korean, and Asian-Indian persons in the United States” (58).

Slavery in America officially ended with Lincoln’s famous “Emancipation Proclamation” in 1863. The Thirteenth Amendment to the US Constitution too declared the abolition of slavery and involuntary servitude. However, the general drive to keep the blacks subservient remained. For instance, several Black Codes were implemented in the Confederate states to retain white authority, supremacy and control. The Codes confined exercise of all rights and privileges like owning properties, marrying, making contracts, testifying in courts – specifically in matters exclusively involving blacks-- only to the whites. Some Codes also prohibited former slaves from changing jobs without the permission of their employers. Pinder rightly argues- “The Black Codes, in their desperate attempt to reinvigorate the slave system of incontestable white supremacy, constrained the life chances of African Americans by maintaining them in structural subordination and dependency” (Pinder 61). Thomas Andrew Bailey, the eminent historian, thought defensively that the Black Codes were actually instrumental in putting the capriciousness of the blacks under check, but in actuality they served to re-cast the previous world of torment and torture, albeit in a sophisticated manner. Consequently, many slaves in the Confederate states tried moving to the North. Interestingly enough, the North also failed to offer the blacks a rescue as there they had to enter into direct competition with the Irish immigrants. The Irish immigrants in the North were already facing discrimination as they were treated as non-whites. When the North saw increasing number of former slaves in the post-Civil War years, the Irish workers found an opportunity to secure their positions by setting them off against the blacks and the

Chinese and “becoming” white by appropriating the privileges accorded to people having white-skin. Takaki aptly remarked- “the North for blacks was not the promised land” (Takaki 110). The Fifteenth Amendment to the US constitution granted voting rights to black men, but the stain of racial discrimination was still indelibly etched in the American psyche. In 1886, the landmark Plessy versus Ferguson case upheld white-privilege by legitimizing and re-establishing racial segregation laws based on the principle that came to be addressed as “separate but equal”.

These factors resulted in whiteness’s gradual advancement to occupy a normative positionality. Pinder rightly comments:

The subordinate position of blacks was the “natural” outcome of white supremacy as a structure that was solidly in place. In fact, blacks and other racialized ethnic groups were not on the opposite side of the racial binary. *All that mattered was white skin. Even the lowest of the lowest whites had something that a non-white person could never possess, which was white skin privilege.* This was how whiteness worked. (65 italics mine)

American “whiteness” was crafted in sundry other ways ranging from documents related to cartography, documents of the visionaries and various captivity narratives and travelogues. Valerie Babb noted in her book how the notion of a truly democratic and pluralistic America that could have been achieved through the close proximity of Europeans, Africans, and Native Americans was “sacrificed to the creation of whiteness” (47). She argued- “In the 1540s...the New World was drawn as an unknown space, dotted with then popular representations of the inhabitants and animals encountered during surveys of eastern Europe, Africa and Asia”(Babb 48). A particular 1544 map, for instance, associated with Sebastian Cabot addressed the eastern part of the New World as “terra incognita” and the pictures there indicated how the European mind sketched the unknown with the erstwhile experiences of conquer and expansionism- “primitive fur-draped people holding spears and a leopard-like animal standing

nearby”(Babb 49). A 1547 map credited to Nicholas Vallard points at a very crucial spot where a colonist directs his attention to the indigenous people and the indigenous person is shown to be very conscious of the group of approaching colonists. The shift in perception from Cabot’s map to Vallard’s shows the possibility of an unfamiliar land’s “white” exploration and colonisation. Likewise, John Smith’s *A Map of Virginia* (1612) showed a world yet to be tarnished by the English and still under the control of the First Nations, but Smith’s maps in his subsequent works like *A Description of New England* (1616) and *Generall historie of Virginia* (1624) make the English presence much more palpable. In 1616 map of Smith, the name “New England” is distinctly visible as is the royal coat of arms. Even the “narratives” of Smith portrayed America as essentially English. *A Map of Virginia*, for instance, stated – “The temperature of this countrie doth agree well with English constitutions being once seasoned to this country” (3). The cartographical details therefore clearly evince how the hitherto “savage” space was transformed by the English minds into a distinctive English space. The transition of Anglicized America to a more general “whitened” one, however occurred with the insurgence of more European nationals to the new land. Babb rightly comments about Smith’s narratives and cartographical details:

In essence, the sense of entitlement expressed in Smith’s accounts accustomed English minds to thinking of the North American continent as theirs for the taking. This proprietary attitude fostered subsequent avowals of English superiority to sustain the belief of English right to North America. As we will see, however, when the advancement of their enterprise became dependent on their casting their lot with those of other white European nationals, assertions of English superiority were replaced by assertions of white superiority. (Babb 57-58)

Another facet of American whiteness that needs to be discussed is the specific English belief in the divine right to possess and rule

North America. “The ethos of divine right laid the attitudinal foundation for American whiteness”, writes Valerie Babb, “by allowing the English to justify the exclusion from full participation in their sanctioned community of those who were not like them, whether because of religious, national or racial differences” (58) The writings of the visionaries who were migrants-turned pilgrims in a new land showed “the growing use of whiteness to represent English social identity” (Babb 59). William Bradford’s *Of Plymouth Plantation*, for example held that America was “devoid of all civil inhabitants, where there are only savage and brutish men which range up and down, little otherwise than the wild beasts of the same”(26). The description of the Native Americans whom Bradford variously named as “Narragansett”, “Mohegan”, and “Pequot” reflect the racially-inflected mind-set of the English Puritans in conceiving of the First Nations and in projecting their own selves as “not savage” as a group. Bradford’s portrayal, therefore, unsettles all dreams of conceiving of America as a homogenized democracy. Cotton Mather, grandson of John Cotton and the son of Increase Mather embodied almost three generations of Puritan theology, thought and social power. Valerie Babb considered Mather’s *Magnalia Christi Americana*, *The Negro Christianized* and *A Good Master Well Served* as the prime books sustaining the Puritan vision. Babb notes – “Though Mather spent much of his time organizing efforts to convert Native Americans and to educate African American slaves, these groups are either excluded from his mytho-history of New England or, in the case of Native Americans, cast as hindering the region’s progress...As such *Magnalia* is one of the first documents to erase American diversity and write America as white”(Babb 63-64). Though Mather tried to reinstate the myth of the pilgrimage of the Puritans coming to the New World in *Magnalia*, his descriptions in the book serve to underscore the racialized enterprise in the pilgrimage. Mather compared his people with the Native Americans asserting “This blessed People was as a little Flock of kids, while there were many Nations of Indians left still as Kennels of Wolves in every corner of the country” (Mather 133). In the sermon, *The Negro Christianized* , Mather remarked about the

slaves, “if they Serve God patiently and cheerfully in the condition which he orders for them, their condition will very quickly be infinitely mended, in Eternal Happiness” (32). In Christianizing “happiness”, Mather’s sermon, therefore, attempted to whitewash the new nation. *A Good Master Well Served* took the “whiteness” impact one step further in associating whiteness with positive values, dreams and ideals such as social mobility and liberation, despite its assertion that there was very negligible difference between white servants and black servants in seventeenth century America. Mather rebuked the employer-masters stating “While you use them [the whites] for Servants, you must so use them, that in Time they may come to be Masters” (12) Even in the captivity narratives and the criminal narratives also, what was facilitated was a cementing of whiteness by creating images of what whiteness is not. Narratives of Mary Rowlandson, John Williams, John Gyles, John Frost, and Cathy N. Davidson are important examples of the same. In the words of Valerie Babb:

Captivity narratives recount intimate encounters between cultures, races, and religions and employ consistent motifs to do so: meek English settlers are beset by savage Native Americans; pious Puritans resist the corruption of papist sects; helpless women and children surmount the vicissitudes of being prisoners in an alien culture. Read over and over because of their drama and popularity, they cemented in readers’ minds conceptions of “us” and “them”. (Babb 68)

“Whiteness” in America therefore came to be constantly shaped, moulded, crafted and reconfigured through the nation’s religious, political, philosophical as well as literary agencies.

Works Cited

Mercer, Kobena, and Bad Object-Choices. "Skin-head sex thing: Racial difference and the homoerotic imaginary." *Hoe do I Look?*, Bay Press, 1991, pp. 169-222.

- Pinder, Sherrow O. "Whiteness: The Definitive Conceptualization of an American Identity." *The Politics of Race and Ethnicity in the United States: Americanization, De-Americanization, and Racialized Ethnic Groups*, Palgrave Macmillan, 2013, pp. 39-65.
- Harris, Cheryl I. "Whiteness as Property." *Harvard Law Review*, vol. 106, no. 8, 1993, p. 1707, *JSTOR*. www.jstor.org/stable/1341787. Accessed 5 Nov. 2016.
- Crevecoeur, Hector St John. *Letters from an American framer*. Edited by Warren B. Blake, E.P. Dutton & CO, 1926.
- Franklin, Benjamin. "Observations Concerning the Increase of Mankind and the Peopling of Countries." *The papers of Benjamin Franklin*, edited by Leonard W. Labaree, Yale U Press, 1961.
- Babb, Valerie M. *Whiteness Visible: The Meaning of Whiteness in American Literature*. NYU P, 1998.
- Bradford, William, and William J. Bradford. *Of Plymouth Plantation, 1620-1647*. Random House, 1981.
- Mather, Cotton. *A Good Master Well Served: Masters and Servants in Colonial Massachusetts, 1620-1750*. B. Green and J. Allen, 1696.